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Atrial Fibrillation Integrated Approach In Frail, Multimorbid, And Polymedicated Older People

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1 Executive Summary

Interactive prototypes allow us to provide visual representations of the iABC platform and are a cost-effective way to test ideas with minimal risk. Using an experienced UNIMAN User Experience expert we can create prototypes that can be provided to interested parties to elicit feedback. This process will be repeated during the development of the iABC platform. This process complements software development and allows a disparate project team to understand what the iABC will look like before software development is complete.

Working with the Arrhythmia Alliance partner we can also seek input on the imagery and wording used in the iABC.

2 Introduction

Interactive prototypes allow us to provide visual representations and are a cost-effective way to test ideas with minimal risk. Using an experienced UNIMAN User Experience expert we can create prototypes that can be provided to interested parties to elicit feedback. This process will be repeated during the development of the iABC platform. This process complements software development and allows a disparate project team to understand what the iABC will look like before software development is complete.

Working with the Arrhythmia Alliance partner we can also seek input on the imagery and wording used in the iABC.

We have provided static images of the prototypes for the purposes of this deliverable.

Note: The content of the prototypes is provided for illustrative purposes only and are not intended to be clinically accurate.

3 Mobile prototypes

Below is a selection of prototypes for the mobile view of the iABC platform and serve as examples for proposed user flow and screen content. This is the platform that will be used by participants on the study.

3.1 Notifications

Notifications will alert the user to specific events. This may be requesting input or simply sign-posting to useful content.

3.2 Adherence

Users can log medication intake to facilitate the display of adherence to prescriptions

3.3 Blood pressure

Users can enter their blood pressure readings for readings taken at home or in a clinical setting and view their historical readings.

3.4 Checklist

A checklist may be a useful way to focus the users' attention on timely items.

3.5 Mobile landing page

One option for when a user first opens the mobile app is to present a clear set of calls-to-action with supporting notifications (as can be seen in the second image).

3.6 Onboarding

The onboarding process will allow users to customise the mobile app. The use of an activation code restricts the ability of the public from accessing the app via the Apple App and Google Play Stores when not participating in the study. Helpful summary screens can also provide the user with at-a-glance information regarding the key features of the app.

3.7 Mobile prescriptions

Users may be able to enter prescriptions in the app and view a summary of their prescriptions.

4 Desktop prototypes

Below is a selection of prototypes for the mobile view of the iABC platform and serve as examples for proposed user flow and screen content. This is the platform that will be used by clinicians in the RCT.

4.1 Adding a new participant

Clinical users will be able to create, edit and delete participants from their logins.

The screenshot displays the 'Add new patients' form within the AFFIRMO application. The interface includes a dark blue sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Patients, Reports, and Settings. The main content area features a search bar at the top, a user profile for Sian Clarke, and the form itself. The form fields are: Name (Henry McGovern), Email address (henry147@gmail.com), Password (v&RB&GStH(NFR112p\$YuuQ96) with a 'Generate password' button), Date of birth (Day: 21, Month: 2, Year: 1949), Gender (radio buttons for Male, Female, Prefer to self identify, Prefer not to say), and Send patient notification (checked checkbox for 'Send the new patient an email about their account'). An 'Add new patient' button is located at the bottom of the form.

4.2 Clinical landing page

A summary page provides the clinician with key metrics relating to their centre and wider study.

4.3 Patient overview

A clinician can see a summary of key metrics relating to individual patients by accessing their record.

4.4 Adding a new prescription

Clinicians can create new prescriptions for a patient which will be used in the adherence calculation. Patients will also be able to see prescriptions created for them. A prescriptions summary page will also provide the clinician with a view across time periods.

The screenshot displays the 'Add new prescription' form in the AFFIRMO application. The interface includes a dark blue sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Patients, Reports, and Settings. The main content area is for patient 'Andre Gilberto', with tabs for Overview, Prescriptions, and Activity. The form fields are as follows:

- Search for patients:** A search bar at the top.
- Drug name:** A text input field containing 'Lisinopril'.
- Drug type:** Radio button options: Tablet, Spray, Inhaler, Injection, Liquid, Suppository.
- Dose amount:** A text input field containing '20'.
- Dose amount unit:** Radio button options: mg, ml, No measurement required.
- Dose frequency:** Radio button options: 1 per day, 2 per day, 3 per day, 4 per day, Specify number of doses.
- Prescription start date:** Three input fields for Day (21), Month (5), and Year (2022).
- Duration:** Radio button options: 1 week, 2 weeks, 3 weeks, 1 month, 2 months, Specify end date.
- Prescription end date:** Three input fields for Day (1), Month (10), and Year (2022).
- Notes:** A text area containing the placeholder text: 'Nulla efficitur nisl et fringilla dignissim. Nullam id turpis vitae ipsum vulputate cursus quis ac dui. In ut turpis et nunc sagittis fermentum nec nec dolor'.

At the bottom of the form is a blue button labeled 'Add new prescription'.

Andre Gilberto

Overview Prescriptions Activity

Prescription history + Add prescription

A new prescription has been added

Drug	Duration	Status
Atorvastatin 20mg, 1 time per day	8/3/2022 - 8/4/2022	Active
Salbutamol 2 doses, 3 times per day	1/9/2021 - 31/5/2022	Active
Latanoprost 1 dose, 1 time per day	1/12/2020 - 28/2/2021	Inactive

Calendar: March 2022

4.5 Patient summary lists

Each clinician will be able to see a list of all patients at their centre.

Patients Filter patients + Add new patient

Study ID	Name	Date of birth	Gender	Status
S001	Joan Bidwell	04 / 10 / 1956	Female	Active
S002	Andre Gilberto	24 / 02 / 1976	Male	Inactive
S003	Fahadh Faasil	13 / 12 / 1941	Male	Active
S004	Anne Davidson	09 / 01 / 1984	Female	Active
S005	Iliuana Todorova	29 / 05 / 1992	Female	Active
S006	Shaun Rockwell	18 / 08 / 1959	Male	Inactive
S007	Lisa Jackson	17 / 07 / 1978	Female	Active
S008	Rachel Monroe	08 / 06 / 1971	Female	Active
S009	Janelle Sissoko	22 / 02 / 1987	Female	Inactive
S010	Nadia Ashraf	27 / 12 / 1984	Female	Inactive

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